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Guidelines for Promoting the Mental Health of Sarasas Affiliated Schools Teacher

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Abstract

This research aimed 1) to study factors, indicators, and methods to promote mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, 2) to study current status, desirable status, and the needs for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, and 3) to propose guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers. The research instrument is a 5-rating scale questionnaire. The data were collected from the sample of 361 persons. Statistics for data analysis include percentage, mean, standard deviation, and coefficient alpha reliability. The findings from the study revealed that 1) according to a synthesis table of content based on the consideration of experts' opinions, there were 3 factors, 7 indicators and 4 development methods, 2) current status for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers was overall at a moderate level, 3) desirable status for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers was overall at the excellent level, 4) the priority of needs of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers as arranged from descending order to ascending order were promoting mental health at work, making good mood to promote interpersonal mental health, accepting other people, promoting one's own mental health, and having good health, 5) guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers consisted of 3 aspects and 20 guidelines, 6) the test results were correct and consistent, 7) the quality assessment results of the guidelines for promoting mental health showed that all aspects were appropriate and possible at a high level.

Keywords: Mental Health Promotion, Sarasas Affiliated School Teachers, Development Guidelines

1. Introduction

The national strategy 2018-2037 elevates the country development in all dimensions to the goal of becoming a developed country driven by wisdom and innovation in the next 20 years. As a consequence, it is necessary to set the basis for human resource development in a systematic manner. Emphasis is placed on developing and uplifting people of all ages in all dimensions to be good, skilled and quality human resources and ready to drive the country forward to its full capacity. "Thai people in the future must be physically, mentally, intellectually, and socially prepared and have good mental health at all ages. Enhancing Thai people to have good health and well-being covers physical, mental, intellectual and social aspects and all forms of well-being management is emphasized, leading to potential in well-being management by oneself. Every sector is supported to participate in enhancing Thai people to have good well-being and appropriate well-being skills. Well-being literacy is created by developing correct and reliable knowledge and well-being communication among people while incorrect well-being knowledge must be monitored and managed, creating intellectual and social skills that increase people's

potential to manage their own well-being, such as modifying one's own health behavior to be proper and having sufficient physical activities for living, preventing and controlling risk factors that threaten well-being by pushing forward all well-being promotion policies that allow all sectors to participate in taking responsibility for people's health so as to reduce threats being obstacles of the development of Thai people's well-being, creating an environment contributing to good well-being, and promoting a health-friendly physical environment (National Strategy, 2018 – 2037).

Thai and global societies are facing new and more complex changes and challenges. Though today's life is full of convenience, people's minds are stimulated by cravings. Many people are suffering and feeling stressed because they are unable to set priority in life. They are looking for something that is not essential since they do not understand their own deep needs. Meanwhile, living in the era of globalization makes people more distant, from family to society levels. Parents do not have time to raise their children while communities and societies trust each other less. Nowadays, there are diseases and health threats causing effects on security, economy, and society in various dimensions, even Thai education system (Department of Mental Health, 2020).

In the current situation, the causes of teachers' mental health and well-being include job satisfaction, social support, and workload, passing through work-family conflicts and work-related stress. A good pattern of relationship is a guideline for express emotional response to students and teacher welfare will be changed in the long term (Split, 2011). Problems of Thai teachers today are overworking in terms of teaching and workloads they need to take responsible for, making them have no time to develop themselves, to have creative ideas or develop instructional media to have quality suitable for promoting learner development (Patcharee Tungkaew et al., 2020).

Teacher development is the key of school transformation. School administrators need to promote teachers to receive knowledge development regarding learning management skills and teacher mental health and well-being development to be ready for learning exchange at all times. Teacher development affects teacher work efficiency, which has a direct effect on educational institutions. Administrators are required to have knowledge, understanding, and capability in promoting work efficiency appropriate to teachers' knowledge and capabilities. Promoting good mental health and well-being of teachers contributes to satisfaction and cooperation in working with administrators, happiness at work to ensure the work of school is successful in an efficient manner. The way teachers have good quality of life, are able to manage both positive and negative feelings efficiently in accordance with their goals, have positive perspectives toward environment and experiences, it will lead to a better way to solve problems and live a life and contribute to self-development at all times, which directly affects goal achievement of the school (Praiya Pengkaew, 2017).

Teachers of Sarasas affiliated schools currently receive economic and social effects over a long period of time, making them have stress, anxiety, emotional fatigue, burnout, work-related life problem, family problem, diseases and health threats, resulting in wide ranging effects. Teacher pressure comes from teaching and learning, working, and social interaction with supervisors/chiefs and colleagues, students, and parents, playing a greater role in teachers' work. Teachers are at risk of mental health problems, which can be seen from social incidents more often. Most teachers face severe problems with their quality of work life, i.e. income and remuneration, safe environment, health promotion, competency development opportunity, progress in their career and job stability, social relations, organizational constitution, independence in work, and pride in the organization. Teachers' problems of quality of work life bring about mental health problems of Sarasas affiliated school teachers at work (Policy from the meeting of school administrators of Sarasas affiliated schools on 20 November 2022).

The researcher viewed the importance and benefits of the preparation of guidelines for the development of mental health and well-being promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers. The information obtained can be used as a guideline for improving the efficiency of administration and management in educational institutions. The objectives of the study were to study factors, indicators, current status, and desirable status for promoting mental health and well-being of Sarasas affiliated school teachers so that school administrators can bring the study results to be guidelines for promoting teachers' mental health and well-being to ensure they are happy at work, satisfied with life, able to deal with both positive and negative feelings efficiently in accordance with current situations. It

will be beneficial to the implementation of a work plan and policy setting for improving the quality of education management to achieve the set goals, bringing the success to the administration of educational institutions.

2. Research objectives

1. To study factors, indicators, and methods to promote mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.
2. To study current status, desirable status, and the needs for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.
3. To propose guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

3. Research methodology

In this research, the researcher focused on studying a guideline for developing mental health and well-being of Sarasas affiliated school teachers. Survey research was conducted and relevant information was studied. A questionnaire was used for data collection.

1. The scope of population

5,798 teachers in 46 Sarasas affiliated schools. The sample size is determined by Krejcie and Morgan Table (1970). The proportion is determined by school. Simple random sampling by a lottery method is used to select the sample. The sample consists of 361 persons.

3.1. *The scope of content*

The researcher focused on studying factors, indicators, and teacher development for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers. There are 3 factors and 7 indicators as follow:

1.1. Promoting mental health at work

- 1) creating good mood at work
- 2) creating the importance of work and work goals
- 3) setting goals to achieve success at work.

1.2 Promoting interpersonal mental health

- 1) building good relationship at work
- 2) accepting other people.

1.3 Promoting one's own mental health

- 1) having good health
- 2) self-control.

3.2. *Teacher development methods*

2.1 Guidance

2.2 Using a mentoring system

2.3 Hands-on learning

2.4 School-based training.

3.3. *Research instrument*

Set 1: **Research instrument**

Part 1 – general information of respondents comes in the form of checklist questions.

Part 2 – questions about current status and desirable status for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers come in the form of a 5-rating scale.

The methods for teacher development come in the form of checklist questions.

Part 3 – opinions and additional suggestions about developing guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

Set 2: The draft of developing guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers

Part 1 – information of respondents, i.e., position, education level, work experience.

Part 2 – inquiries about experts' opinions about appropriateness, feasibility, and usability of the draft of developing guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

3.4. Making and testing the instrument

1. Study how to make a questionnaire used for data collection from documents and textbooks relevant to a guideline for improving teachers' mental health.
2. Study relevant concepts, theories and research documents, consider details to ensure they cover all the research objectives.
3. Make a questionnaire to cover all research objectives to be used as the instrument to collect data from the sample for making an analysis accordingly.
4. Submit the questionnaire to the advisor to verify accuracy and appropriateness in order to improve it to be complete.
5. Measure the validity of the instrument. The made questionnaire is submitted to 5 experts; experts in school administration, to check the accuracy and assess that that content is clear, correct, and consistent with the definition. IOC was set at 0.60 or higher. All question items met the criteria, the IOC was 1.00.
6. The questionnaire verified by the experts was measured the power of discrimination and pretested with 30 people who are not the research sample. Internal consistency was measured. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to measure the power of discrimination. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used to measure the reliability of the questionnaire. The reliability of the questionnaire was 0.98.

3.5. Data analysis

1. Analyze the status of the respondents by calculating frequency and percentage.
2. Analyze the current status and desirable status of the development guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers by calculating mean, standard deviation, and interpreting levels. The questionnaire came from a rating scale, interpreted by comparing with the 5 rating scales as follow (Boonchom Srisa-ard, 2013, page 121):
3. The needs analysis (Modified Priority Needs Index: PNI modified) of teacher development according to the concept of mental health promotion so as to arrange the priority. The results obtained would be used to design teacher development guidelines in accordance with the concept about mental health promotion.
4. Analyze opinions and additional suggestions about mental health promotion in school using descriptive analysis.
5. Descriptive statistics, i.e., frequency and percentage were used to analyze methods for teacher development to promote mental health in school.

3.6. Statistics in data analysis

Statistics used in data processing and analysis are as follow:

1. Basic statistics, i.e., percentage, mean, and standard deviation.
2. Statistics used to measure the quality of the instrument, i.e., IOC (Index of item objective congruence. Cronbach's alpha coefficient is used to measure reliability of the questionnaire.
3. Statistics used to identify the needs of teacher development in accordance with the concept of mental health promotion to set the priority, (Modified Priority Needs Index: PNI modified).

4. Data analysis results

The analysis results are presented procedurally as per the following details:

4.1. Part 1 presents the data analysis results of the study on factors, indicators, and methods promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

Factors, indicators, and methods for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers obtained from the synthesis of relevant documents, theoretical concepts, and research studies conducted domestically and internationally, performed by making a synthetic table of content and using consideration of criteria selected by experts as factors, indicators, and development methods more than 50%. It was found that there were 3 factors, 7 indicators and 4 methods for teacher development.

4.2. Part 2 presents the data analysis results of the study on current status, desirable status and the needs of promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

2.1 The analysis results of the current status, desirable status and the needs of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers were obtained from the sample of 361 persons. The analysis was performed to find out mean, standard deviation, current status, desirable status, and the needs of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

Table 4.3: Mean, standard deviation and interpretation, current status, desirable status, mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers (n = 361).

Mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers		Current status			Desirable status		
		$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret results	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Interpret results
(n = 361)							
1. Promoting mental health at work							
1.1	Creating a good mood at work	2.96	0.67	Moderate	4.47	0.51	High
1.2	Setting importance and goals at work	3.05	0.61	Moderate	4.42	0.60	High
1.3	Setting goals for success at work	2.99	0.59	Moderate	4.35	0.62	High
Total		3.00	0.62	Moderate	4.41	0.57	High
2. Promoting interpersonal mental health							
2.1	Building a good relationship with others at work	3.13	0.78	Moderate	4.40	0.60	High
2.2	Accepting other people	3.08	0.61	Moderate	4.39	0.61	High
Total		3.41	0.69	Moderate	4.39	0.60	High
3. Promoting one's own mental health							
3.1	Having good health	3.01	0.77	Moderate	4.37	0.65	High
3.2	self-control	3.07	0.61	Moderate	4.35	0.62	High
Total		3.04	0.69	Moderate	4.36	0.63	High
Total		3.15	0.66	Moderate	4.38	0.60	High

According to Table 4.3, it was found that the current status of mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers was overall at a moderate level ($\bar{x} = 3.15$, S.D. = 0.66). When each aspect was taken into consideration, the aspect with the highest mean at a moderate level was promoting interpersonal mental health ($\bar{x} = 3.41$, S.D. = 0.69) and the aspect with the lowest mean at a moderate level was promoting mental health at work ($\bar{x} = 3.00$, S.D. = 0.62).

With regard to desirable status of mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, overall it was at a high level ($\bar{x} = 4.38$, S.D. = 0.60). When each aspect was taken into consideration, the aspect with the highest

mean at a high level was promoting mental health at work ($\bar{x} = 4.41$, S.D. = 0.57), and the aspect with the lowest mean at a high level was promoting one's own mental health ($\bar{x} = 4.36$, S.D. = 0.63).

The analysis results of the needs of mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers that shall lead to guidelines for developing mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers can be concluded as follow:

The needs of guidelines for developing mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers were analyzed to set the priority (Modified Priority Needs Index: PNI modified) for designing guidelines for developing mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

Table 2 shows the mean of current status, the mean of desirable status of guidelines for developing mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, modified priority needs index and the priority needs of each aspect.

Table 4.11: The mean of current status, desirable status, priority needs index, and overall priority needs and the priority needs of each aspect

(n=361)

Mental health promotion	D	I	PNI modified	Priority needs
1. Mental health at work				
1.1 Creating a good mood at work	2.96	4.47	0.510	1
1.2 Setting importance and goals at work	3.05	4.42	0.449	4
1.3 Setting goals for success at work	2.99	4.35	0.454	2
Total	3.00	4.41	0.470	1
2. Promoting interpersonal mental health				
2.1 Building a good relationship with others at work	3.13	4.40	0.405	7
2.2 Accepting other people	3.08	4.39	0.425	5
Total	3.41	4.39	0.287	3

Table 4.11: The mean of current status, desirable status, priority needs index, and overall priority needs and the priority needs of each aspect (continued)

(n=361)

Mental health promotion	D	I	PNI modified	Priority needs
3. Promoting one's own mental health				
3.1 Having good health	3.01	4.37	0.451	3
3.2 Self-control	3.07	4.35	0.416	6
Total	3.04	4.36	0.434	2
Total (X_{tot})	3.15	4.38	0.390	

According to Table 4.11, the priority needs of the guidelines for developing mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, overall and each aspect, from descending to ascending order are mental health promotion at work; creating good mood at work, followed by promoting one's own mental health; having good health, promoting interpersonal mental health; accepting other people respectively.

The needs of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers in each aspect are as follow:

1. Promoting mental health at work consists of

1.1 Creating a good mood at work. Teachers are able to have satisfaction and happiness at work. They are able to relieve stress by themselves while they are working. They are able to accept problem status, obstacles at work and solve work-related problems by themselves.

1.2 Setting importance and goals at work. Teachers are able to trust other people and give importance to work. They dare enough to express their opinions and listen to opinions of others. They develop themselves and search for knowledge and bring the knowledge obtained to practice in class and school regularly.

1.3 Setting goals for success at work. Teachers have knowledge and understanding to make a plan for integrated learning management appropriate to students' age. They have knowledge and skills in using media and academic sources in an efficient manner. They have knowledge, understanding and skills in management, design, planning to develop their own teaching and learning management effectively.

2. Promoting interpersonal mental health consists of

2.1 Building a good relationship with others at work. Teachers are able to transfer and share teaching techniques and work experiences with colleagues. They are able to solve problems, express their opinions and suggestions with colleagues at school.

2.2 Accepting other people. Teachers participate in designing a new process of teaching and learning management with a teacher team, which can be applied to school. They are able to accept colleagues' opinions or opinions of other people that are different from theirs. They are able to adapt themselves to the environment at work when working with a group of teachers having different backgrounds in an appropriate manner.

3. Promoting one's own mental health consists of

3.1 Having good health. Teachers need to have physical checkup and exercise regularly. They are able to manage working time and workload suitable for their potential at work, not affecting their own health. They need to take care of their health, relieve anxiety for being ready to learn and develop their work ability.

3.2 Self-control. Teachers are able to control their emotions when a crisis or serious problem occurs. They are able to make decision or choose an appropriate work method suitable under the rules and regulations of the school. They are flexible and patient with improper behavior of others by expressing positive emotions.

4.3. Part 3 presents the analysis results of data studied, prepare, examine and assess the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

The study results show the priority needs index (PNI modified) from descending to ascending order as follow: Promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work, promoting interpersonal mental health; accepting other people, promoting one's own mental health; having good health to make an interview form to seek guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers. The target persons of the interview were 1 director and 1 administrator in 3 schools, 6 persons in total. A purposive sampling method was used to select the target persons. The schools selected must have best practice about the development of guidelines for promoting teachers' mental health. The schools must achieve excellent management, leading to the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

5. Conclusion

The research results of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers can be concluded as follow:

5.1. The study on factors, indicators, and methods for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

1.1 According to the synthesis of documents, research, concepts, theories conducted domestically and internationally, it was found that there are 3 factors, 7 indicators and 4 methods for promoting teachers' mental health.

5.2. The analysis results of current status, desirable status and the needs of the development of guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

2.1 The analysis results can be concluded as follow:

1) the overall current status of mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers was at a moderate level. When each aspect was taken into consideration, the aspect with the highest mean at a moderate level was promoting interpersonal mental health and the aspect with the lowest mean at a moderate level was promoting mental health at work.

2) as for desirable status of mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, overall it was at a high level. When each aspect was taken into consideration, the aspect with the highest mean at a high level was promoting mental health at work and the aspect with the lowest mean was promoting one's own mental health.

2.2 The analysis results of the priority needs of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

Overall and each aspect, from descending to ascending orders are mental health at work; creating a good mood at work, followed by promoting one 's own mental health; having good health, promoting interpersonal health; accepting other people respectively.

2.3 Data analysis of methods to promote mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

With regard to promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work, most of them gave viewed that teachers should learn from working, followed by pieces of advice, school-based training, and mentoring system.

In relationship promoting one's own mental health; having good health, most of them viewed that teachers should learn from working, followed by pieces of advice, school-based training, and mentoring system.

With regard to promoting interpersonal mental health; accepting other people, most of them viewed that teachers should learn from working, followed by pieces of advice, school-based training, and mentoring system.

5.3. The study on guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers

3.1 The study results on the highest PNI modified of all aspects were used to make an interview form, as arranged from descending to ascending order as follow: 1. Promoting mental health at work. 2. Promoting one's own mental health. 3. Promoting interpersonal mental health to develop mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers. The schools achieve best practice about the development of guidelines for promoting teachers' mental health, have excellent management that leads to the guidelines for promoting teachers' mental health.

3.2 Results of the draft of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers.

Obtained from the study on the needs of the development, best practice, and synthesis by the researcher, showed that there are 3 aspects 20 guidelines.

3.4 The results of the examination confirming accuracy and consistency of the guidelines for improvement according to experts' advice to obtain the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers showed there are 3 aspects and 20 guidelines.

3.5 The quality assessment results of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers found that there are 20 guidelines which are appropriate and feasible to be used to promote mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers. The mean was 4.40 and 4.20 respectively.

6. Discussion

According to the study on guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, it can be discussed as follow:

6.1. Current status and desirable status of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers according to Sarasas affiliated school teachers are shown below:

1.1 With regard to current stats of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, when each aspect was taken into consideration, the aspect with the highest mean was promoting interpersonal mental health. It is the number one to be developed since today's society is changing at all times. Importance is given to acceptance of differences, building trust in others, participation in groups, adaptability to environment, participation in designing new processes of teaching and learning management with a teacher team to be applied to school, accepting performance assessments from others, and being able to use the assessment results to improve and develop one's own work. This is consistent with a research study conducted by Tanaporn Suwanworabun (2020) on work-related happiness and general well-being of personnel in addiction management as the study result indicated that their happiness and general well-being were at a moderate level.

1.2 With reference to desirable status of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, when each aspect was taken into consideration, the aspect with the highest mean was promoting mental health at work. It is the number one to be developed because administrators are aware of the importance of promoting teachers to be able to create nice atmosphere and environment for teaching and learning, take pride in the tasks assigned, have satisfaction and happiness at work, accept problems and obstacles that occur at work and be able to solve problems, control their emotions when problems arise, and relieve work-related stress by themselves. This is consistent with a research study conducted by Phra Palad Anon Changrangkarn (2021).

5.2. The priority needs of the guidelines for developing mental health promotion of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, from descending to ascending order, are promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work, followed by promoting one's own mental health; having good health, promoting interpersonal mental health; accepting other people respectively.

2.1 Promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work is the top priority because teachers are required to create nice atmosphere and environment at work by making a mechanism to ensure teachers take pride in and are happy at work. They accept problems and obstacles that can happen at work and seek a way to solve the problems. This is consistent with a study conducted by Gito et al. (2013).

2.2 Promoting one's own mental health; having good health, is necessary to be developed to encourage teachers to manage work time, workload to be suitable for their working potential by not affecting their health. They are able to take care of their health, relieve stress and anxiety, and get ready to learn and develop their work ability. This is consistent with a study conducted by McCauley (1998).

2.3 Promoting interpersonal mental health; accepting other people, is necessary to be developed. Teachers are required to participate in designing a new process of teaching and learning management with a teacher team to be applied to school. They are able to accept colleagues' opinions and trust other people to perform important tasks of school in an appropriate manner. The quality of teachers must be uplifted systematically and continuously so that they will have knowledge and skills for confronting different situations to ensure their work can achieve the organizational goals efficiently. This is consistent with a study conducted by Praiya Pengkaew (2017).

It can be concluded that the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers consist of 3 aspects, namely, promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work, promoting one's own mental health; having good health, promoting interpersonal mental health; accepting other people. School administrators can use the guidelines to make a plan consistent with their needs to promote mental health of teachers in Sarasas affiliated schools to achieve the school goals.

5.3 Suggestion

5.3.1 General suggestion

According to the study results and discussion mentioned above, it was found that current status and desirable status and the needs of the guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers, from descending to ascending order, are promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work, promoting one's own

mental health; having good health, promoting interpersonal mental health; accepting other people can be applied to achieve the goals in mental health development of teachers in Sarasas affiliated schools as follow:

1) Promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work is the number one to be developed. Therefore, school administrators and relevant agencies should promote teacher to learn from working, teacher development training should be organized for teachers to be able to create nice atmosphere and environment at work, take pride in the tasks assigned, have satisfaction with and happiness at work, accept problems and obstacles happen to work and be able to solve the problems, be able to control their emotions and relieve stress and anxiety by themselves while working.

2) Schools should prepare a teacher development project on guidelines for promoting mental health of teachers in Sarasas affiliated schools. Training should be provided to give knowledge for handling and solving problems in a correct way. Mental health affects the quality of work and learning management for students. If teachers have mental health problems, they will have negative feelings towards work, making their work efficiency decline including teaching management which is the main duty of schools.

5.3.2 Suggestion for future research

5.3.2.1 A study should be conducted on factors affecting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers to understand basic status and individual differences and to obtain a higher quality guideline for developing teachers in Sarasas affiliated schools that meets individual differences. According to the research results, mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers was overall at a high level. When the mean of each aspect was analyzed, it was found that each aspect had different means. Therefore, a study should be conducted on individual factors affecting mental health, such as individual belief, attitude, and goals in life.

5.3.2.2 A study should be conducted on factors affecting work efficiency of teachers in schools with different context from schools affiliated to Bangkok Metropolitan Administration, such as private schools and other organization to obtain a guideline for promoting mental health in accordance with appropriateness and feasibility of various context. The research results revealed that Sarasas affiliated school teachers have the number one need in promoting mental health at work; creating a good mood at work. In this regard, a study should be conducted on mental health in the point related to creating a good mood at work among teachers in different context to generate a guideline for promoting mental health of teachers in Sarasas affiliated schools that meets the context of the school.

5.3.2.3 The guidelines for promoting mental health of Sarasas affiliated school teachers should be tried out with a sample while the efficiency and effectiveness of mental health promotion should be assessed after the test so that the guidelines shall be improved and developed accordingly.

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References

- Department of Mental Health. (2020). Turn bad into good, RQ mental health power. The 4th edition. Bangkok: Beyond Publishing Co.,Ltd.
- National Strategy. (2018). National Strategy 2018 – 2037. National Strategy Secretariat Office. Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council.

- Songsamorn Sota. (2017). Psychological well-being, positive thinking, work values and commitment to organization of the secondary school teachers at Pakkret, Nonthaburi province. *Srinakharinwirot Research and Development (Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 18, 60-71.
- Praiya Pengkaew. (2017). Early childhood teacher development based on the concept of promoting mental well-being. Department of Educational Administration, Chulalongkorn University.
- National Mental Health Development Plan No.1 (2018 – 2037). Mental Health Strategy and Planning Division. Department of Mental Health. Mental Health Knowledge Base, accessed November 4, 2023.
- Phra Palad Anon Changrangkarn (2021). The development of psychological well-being of registered nurses through Buddhist group counseling. The study according to the Doctor of Philosophy Program in Counseling Psychology, Faculty of Education, Burapha University.
- Tanaporn Suwanworaboon. (2020). Work-related happiness and general well-being of personnel in addiction management. A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Master of Science Program in Mental Health, Department of Psychiatry, Faculty of Medicine, Chulalongkorn University.
- Patcharee Tungaew et al., (2020). *The study and development of model a strengthen resilience and rehabilitation integrated of teachers and educational personnel on new normal*. Research of Office of the Welfare Promotion Commission for Teachers and Educational Personnel, Ministry of Education, the fiscal year 2020.
- Gito, M., Ihara, H., & Ogata, H. (2013). The relationship of resilience, hardiness, depression and burnout among Japanese psychiatric hospital nurses. *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, 3(11), 12-18.
- McCauley, C. D. (1998). *The Center for Creative Leadership Handbook of Leadership Development*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Spilt, L. J., Koomen M. Y. H. & Thijs T. J. (2011). *Teacher Wellbeing: The Importance of Teacher-Student Relationships*. Department of Developmental Psychology University of Amsterdam.